

High-throughput microstructure characterization of compositionally graded Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr complex concentrated alloys (CCA) prepared by laser directed energy deposition

T. Krajnák^{a,b,*}, D. Preisler^a, J. Kout^{c,d}, J. Stráský^a, M. Janeček^a, M.C. Luna^a,
M. Šlapáková^a, J. Kozlík^a, P. Harcuba^a, J. Džugan^c

^a Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Ke Karlovu 3, 121 16 Praha 2, Czech Republic

^b Research Centre, University of Žilina, Univerzitná 1, Žilina, 01026, Slovakia

^c Comtes FHT, Průmyslová 996, Dobruška, 334 41, Czech Republic

^d Department of Metals and Corrosion Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology, Technická 5, Prague 6, 166 28, Prague, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Systematic variation of chemical compositions in quaternary Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr based complex concentrated alloys was achieved through the additive manufacturing technique of laser directed energy deposition (L-DED). Two separate feeders containing binary equimolar mixtures of elemental powders (CrNb/TiZr and CrZr/TiNb) were used simultaneously for deposition of gradient samples on thermally insulated substrate plate. The compositions ranging from approx. 5 to approx. 45 at. % for each element were obtained in the deposited samples. Investigation of the chemical composition effects on the phase content after homogenization heat treatment at 1200 °C, within one individual sample, was performed using microhardness measurements, XRD and EDS techniques and microstructural observations by SEM. Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr single-phase/multi-phase regions in the studied quaternary phase diagram were determined. Multi-phase regions contain Cr-rich BCC Laves type phase of varying composition as determined by the chemical composition of the matrix. The presence of the BCC Laves type phase in multi-phase areas was confirmed by CALPHAD simulations. The L-DED technique was found to be capable of producing compositionally graded complex concentrated alloys on the basis of refractory elemental powders with high melting temperatures for the high-throughput microstructure characterization.

1. Introduction

Modern materials must be able to withstand extreme temperatures and operate reliably across a wide variety of industrial applications and environments [1]. In addition, the rapid growth of AI-driven applications, which rely heavily on large-scale data centers, presents significant challenges for energy generation [2]. Furthermore, the worldwide increase in military spendings presents another challenge for material scientists and engineers in developing new high-performance materials. Robust performance at high temperatures is critical for meeting the material requirements of these increasingly demanding applications [3].

As stated in numerous articles, refractory complex concentrated alloys (RCCAs) and high-entropy alloys (RHEAs) containing multiple principal elements were proposed as a new group of materials capable of withstanding extreme temperatures in these harsh operating

environments [4–7]. Nonetheless, the development of these materials into viable components and devices for extreme temperature applications poses formidable obstacles [8]. Owing to the low workability, extreme melting points of the constituent elements, high affinity to oxygen at elevated temperatures, and very high cost of raw input materials, the manufacturing of RCCAs via conventional metallurgy techniques is challenging, time-consuming, and expensive. Hence, only a limited number of such alloys have been produced and inspected [5,9].

One potential solution is to employ near-net-shape fabrication techniques, such as 3D printing methods, in which localized melting of the material is achieved using lasers or electron beams [10–12]. Additive manufacturing, namely directed energy deposition, allows for the rapid synthesis and evaluation of a wide range of compositional variants of these complex alloy systems [13], potentially accelerating the material development process [14]. Owing to the layer-by-layer deposition

* Corresponding author. Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Ke Karlovu 3, 121 16 Praha 2, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: tomas.krajnak@matfyz.cuni.cz (T. Krajnák).

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Table 1
The size and the chemical composition of powders used for 3D printing.

Powder	Ti grade 2	Cr (99.9 %)	Nb (99.9 %)	Zr (99.9 %)
Suppliers	(AP&C, Canada)	(Stanford Adv. Materials, USA)	CAMEX, Czech Republic	
Particle size	45–150 μm	50–150 μm		
Content of elements in wt%				
O	0.17	0.02	0.15	0.22
N	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.03

Fig. 1. The tetrahedron of quaternary Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr system. The black points represent the target chemical compositions achieved by printing from two separate feeders containing binary equimolar mixtures of powders CrNb/TiZr and CrZr/TiNb.

process, the chemical composition of each printed layer can be precisely controlled, thereby enabling the fabrication of functional compositional gradients within a single part [15]. Moorehead et al. [16] stated that additive manufacturing could dramatically accelerate material development, potentially reducing the processing time by up to 100 times compared to traditional manufacturing methods. This high-throughput approach to material discovery may be especially valuable when

combined with methods of thermodynamic modelling that can screen and identify new promising CCA compositions [17–21]. Nonetheless, given the limited data on the kinetics and formation of metastable phases, experimental validation of the predicted phases is necessary [17, 22]. However, the fabrication of compositional gradients requires the use of elemental powders, which presents another set of complications due to major differences between the melting points and other physical properties of individual elements [23]. Deposition from the elemental powders results in various defects which include elemental segregation, lack of fusion, and residual porosity [24–26]. Nevertheless, numerous studies have shown that the use of elemental powders to produce compact homogenous RHEA samples is viable when processing parameters are carefully optimized [16, 23–25, 27–32].

Several recent studies have demonstrated the feasibility of using directed energy deposition for the fabrication of compositionally graded samples of refractory complex concentrated alloys [29, 30, 32]. For instance, Melia et al. [32] successfully produced graded samples of a Mo–Nb–Ta–W system using in-situ alloying of elemental powders by DED. Döbelstein et al. [29] successfully fabricated a thin-wall specimen of a quaternary system Nb–Ta–Ti–Zr with varying chemical composition from $\text{Ti}_{25}\text{Zr}_{50}\text{Nb}_0\text{Ta}_{25}$ to $\text{Ti}_{25}\text{Zr}_0\text{Nb}_{50}\text{Ta}_{25}$. Furthermore, the same research group fabricated columnar samples with compositional gradients by vertically stacking spot welds. In this study, the researchers explored the compositional space of the quinary Hf–Nb–Ta–Ti–Zr system by varying the composition of one element at a time, while keeping the others at equimolar proportions [30]. However, the papers focusing on the preparation of bulk compositionally graded RCCAs are scarce.

It was shown, that despite excellent high temperature strength, RCCAs can exhibit poor oxidation resistance [33, 34]. To address this challenge, the incorporation of reactive elements such as chromium into the alloy composition may improve oxidation resistance by forming a protective layer of chromium oxide [35, 36].

The presented paper focuses on a systematic characterization of the chemical composition and related microstructure and phase evolution across the compositionally graded quaternary Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr CCA prepared by L-DED technique. The most obvious strategy to prepare compositionally graded CCAs containing four elements is to use elemental powders and mix them arbitrarily during deposition using four different powder containers (hoppers), each containing a single element. However, using four independent hoppers is technologically demanding; and most importantly there is a technological limit of powder feeders – below some minimum feeding rate, it is impossible to

Fig. 2. (a) The experimental setup used for the sample deposition and (b) the schematic image of the deposited sample showing the positions of the performed experiments.

Fig. 3. Low-mag light micrographs in the whole cross-section of the (a) Grad 1, (b) Grad 2, (c) Grad 3 and (d) Grad 4 as-deposited samples. Undissolved Nb particles are denoted by red arrows.

control the flow of the powder precisely. Based on various experiments and approaches aiming to overcome these limitations, we propose a strategy for exploring the quaternary composition using only two hoppers, each with an equimolar mixture of two elements out of the four. Deposition from the two hoppers allows deposition at higher feeding rates, which leads to the more precise control of chemical composition. Moreover, such an approach enables reaching the wider range of compositions. Further, a systematic approach for microstructural characterization has been utilized. A set of microhardness indents made along the building direction ensures the precise orientation within the sample for subsequent microstructural observations at the same zone.

2. Materials and method

Compositionally graded Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr complex concentrated alloys were deposited via commercially available apparatus Insstek MX-Lab equipped with Ytterbium fibre laser source at the maximum power of 500 W. Nominal layer height of 150 μm , ZigZag link CF/CFC printing strategy (rotation by 90° between the successive layers), print speed of 850 mm/min and a hatch distance of 300 μm were used for sample deposition. Given the laser beam diameter of 400 μm , these printing conditions yield the 100 μm overlay of the adjacent runs. The designation "Zig-Zag link CF/CFC" means that during the deposition, the contour (C) of the layer is deposited first, followed by the filling (F) using the ZigZag scans. Similarly, in the next layer, the additional contour is deposited after the filling, without switching-off the laser at any point during the deposition. The chemical composition and the particles size distribution of the commercially available elemental powders used in this study are listed in Table 1. Particles of all elemental powders have spherical shape [37].

Binary equimolar mixtures of the powders CrNb, CrZr, TiZr and TiNb were used for the preparation of the compositional gradient samples.

Before deposition, the equimolar mixture of the two elemental powders was mixed three times for 1 h in a laboratory mechanical mixer. Composition gradient was achieved by in-situ mixing of the two pre-mixed powder blends (CrNb–TiZr and CrZr–NbTi) during deposition. Fig. 1 shows the tetrahedron of quaternary Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr system and explorable compositions generated by this strategy, considering the limitations of powder feeders.

Considering the fact, that bottom of the sample differs from the top in terms of thermal history and microstructure even in homogeneous CrNbTiZr alloy [37], the two combinations of pre-mixed powder blends allow for the deposition of four different gradients: Grad 1: CrNb (bottom) \rightarrow TiZr (top), Grad 2: TiZr (bottom) \rightarrow CrNb (top), Grad 3: CrZr (bottom) \rightarrow TiNb (top) and Grad 4: TiNb (bottom) – CrZr (top). Powders were supplied from two separate feeders. The powder flow was regulated by a vibration system. Initially the feeding rate was set to 0.5 g/min for feeder 1, while feeder 2 was inactive. After depositing of 10 layers, corresponding to approximately 1.5 mm of material thickness, the feeding rate of feeder 2 began to incrementally increase after each layer, while the feeding rate of the feeder 1 simultaneously decreased.

The deposition was performed in the argon protective atmosphere of the purity of 99.9999 %. The argon flow was automatically controlled during the deposition, to keep the oxygen content well below 100 ppm. The oxygen content was monitored using a built-in sensor based on an electrochemical cell. Typical oxygen content in the chamber of around 45 ppm was held also for 2 h after the end of the deposition to prevent the contamination by oxygen and nitrogen during the sample cooling. Furthermore, the area of the melt pool was locally shielded by Ar flowing from the deposition head with the flow of 8 l/min. The gas flow transporting the powder to the melt pool was set to 3 l/min. Solid blocks having the square shape base of 10 \times 10 mm² and the final height of 6–11 mm were produced. The deposition occurred directly to the Ti Grade 2, 5 mm thick plate, that was thermally insulated from the

Fig. 4. Electron back-scatter SEM images of the Grad 1, Grad 2 and Grad 4 samples in the (a)(d)(g) bottom, (b)(e)(h) middle (c)(f)(i) top part, respectively. Un-dissolved or partly melted Zr and Nb particles are denoted by red and black arrows, respectively.

underlaid platform by the ceramic fibre insulating plate Ultraboard 1850-400 (80 % $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 20\% \text{SiO}_2$) by Schupp (Aachen, Germany) with specified thermal conductivity of 0.34 W/mK. The ceramic fibre insulating plate had a thickness of 40 mm. As a result, the temperature of thermally insulated platform, that was heated by the residual deposition heat, reached 500 °C during the deposition. Deposition at elevated temperatures effectively eliminates temperature gradient formed at the edges of the melt pool and thus prevents the crack formation. The experimental setup with thermally insulated platform is shown in Fig. 2a.

Each sample in the as-deposited condition was cut along the building direction into two identical halves. The plane of this central cut (i.e. the xz plane, as shown in Fig. 2b) was used for the investigation. To dissolve unmelted Nb particles present in as-deposited state, one half of the sample underwent homogenization heat treatment at 1200 °C/180 h in 99.9999 % Ar atmosphere (in a vertical tube furnace Nabertherm RHTV 120–600/18) followed by a water quench. The temperature and time of heat treatment was selected according to the results in Ref. [37]. The sample preparation of as-deposited and heat-treated samples consists of the mechanical grinding of the xz plane using SiC papers with decreasing grit size down to the 5 μm , followed by gentle polishing for 7 min by 20 % solution of hydrogen peroxide in OP-S colloidal silica suspension. First, microhardness was measured along three lines on both as deposited and annealed samples (see Fig. 2b). The distance between the successive indents along the line was set to 250 μm . EDS strip having the width of 270 μm was measured along the central line of both samples.

Microhardness indents helped to trace the positions of subsequent experiments. SEM image and EDS mapping were taken next to each indent along the central line of annealed samples. Finally, X-ray diffraction was performed on homogenized material at four positions along the central line. One measurement in the single-phase area (middle part of the sample) and three measurements in the multi-phase area (bottom, middle and top part of the band of secondary particles) were performed. The spot with the diameter of 0.3 mm and in-place camera for precise selection of the investigated area on the sample surface were employed. Microhardness measurements were performed under the applied load of 500 g and a dwell time of 10 s employing automatic microhardness tester Qness Q10A. SEM FEI Quanta 200 and Apreo 2 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) electron microscopes equipped with EDAX EDS detectors and diffractometer Rigaku Rapid II with a sealed Mo tube, $\text{MoK}\alpha$ graphite monochromator and curved 2D detector for measurement in reflection mode were used. The position of the Mo tube was fixed at the angle of 7°. The rocking of the sample in φ and χ axes was employed for better statistics. To compare the phase content determined by the used experimental methods, calculations by CALPHAD method were performed with the commercial ThermoCalc software (ver. 2022b) using a database TCHEA4, containing all binary combinations of CrNbTiZr as well as two ternaries: CrTiZr and NbTiZr. The phase content was evaluated for two of the studied samples, Grad 2 and Grad 4. For each of them, one chemical composition in the single-phase region and two compositions in the two-phase region were selected. The calculations were performed between 700 °C and 1500 °C.

Fig. 5. Chemical composition evolution across the height of the samples (z-axis) evaluated from EDS strip (a) as-deposited Grad 1 sample, (b) annealed Grad 1 sample, (c) as-deposited Grad 2 sample and (d) annealed Grad 2 sample and (e) as-deposited Grad 4 and (f) annealed Grad 4 sample.

Fig. 6. Backscatter SEM images of the interface between the single and multi-phase area of the (a) Grad 1, (b) Grad 2, (c) Grad 4 samples. Left-hand side of the images corresponds to the bottom part of the sample.

3. Experimental results and discussion

3.1. Microstructure of as-deposited samples

Microstructure overview of the as-deposited samples is shown in the low magnification light microscopy (LM) images (Fig. 3). The macro-cracks are clearly visible in the bottom of the Grad 1 sample (a) and at the top part of the Grad 2 sample (b) and Grad 3 sample (c). In contrast, in the Grad 4 sample (d) only one smaller macro-crack in the deposition direction in the central part of the sample is present. Black dots denoted by red arrows correspond to the undissolved Nb particles. The height of the individual samples differs significantly, while, the height of the Grad 3 and Grade 4 samples is comparable. As shown and discussed below the Grad 1 and Grad 2 samples give the equivalent results, that are mutually inverse with respect to the building direction. To avoid the repetition, the results obtained on the Grad 3 sample will not be presented as they are similar to those for the Grad 4 sample.

Microstructure observations along the 3D printed samples shown in Fig. 4 revealed the presence of undissolved or partly melted Zr particles (denoted by red arrows) in the Grad 1 sample. The number of these particles increases with increasing sample height. This is consistent with increasing amount of the Zr along the deposition direction (z -direction) as shown later. On the other hand, almost no undissolved or partly melted Zr particles were observed in the Grad 2/Grad 4 samples. These Zr particles are smaller than Nb particles hence not visible in LM (cf. Fig. 3a–c). Vice-versa, given the magnification of SEM, the undissolved Nb particles (denoted by black arrows) were observed only occasionally in all samples. In addition, the microstructure of all samples seems to be locally chemically homogeneous, and the contrast between the neighbouring layers is not apparent. The long-term homogenization heat treatment effectively dissolved unmelted Zr and Nb particles, thus no residual particles (not shown here) were observed in the homogenized samples.

3.2. Chemical composition evolution in as-deposited and annealed samples

EDS lines plotted in Fig. 5 represent the chemical composition evolution along the height of Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr CCA in as-deposited and annealed conditions. Left-hand side of the plots correspond to the bottom of the samples. The gradients presented in Fig. 1 were successfully achieved in compositions ranging from approx. 5 to approx. 45 at. % for each element. Prepared samples therefore allow for efficient investigations over a wide range of compositions. However, the gradients were nominally designed to be linear, which was not achieved due to both fundamental and technological reasons. Technological reasons include imprecision in powder feeding and a slight elemental separation in the individual powder hoppers. Fundamental reasons include

evaporation of Cr during deposition and formation of secondary Cr-rich Laves phase (mainly after annealing) and associated diffusion processes; both these issues are discussed in detail below.

As shown in Fig. 5a, the concentration of CrNb in as-deposited sample decreases continuously from about 40 at. % towards approx. 3 % for both Cr and Nb. Moreover, the content of Cr and Nb is the same at each position. On the other hand, in the Grad 2 sample, namely in the upper half part, the amount of Cr is lower than its counterpart Nb from the same hopper. Similarly, in the Grad 4 sample, Cr content is lower than Zr despite using the same hopper. This lack of Cr is attributed to the Cr evaporation during deposition. It is assumed that the evaporation is more pronounced in the upper part of the sample. Note that in both Grad 2 and Grad 4 samples, the nominal content of Cr increases with the sample height. Conversely, in the Grad 1 sample such unwanted difference between Cr and Nb does not occur. It is therefore obvious that the combination of the powders which are fed from a single hopper and a chosen direction of gradient significantly affect the final chemical composition evolution in the deposited compositionally graded samples. It can be recommended to start from a higher concentration of a potentially evaporating element in the bottom of the sample.

The homogenization treatment of the gradient samples preserves the overall concentration gradients in all samples (cf. Fig. 5b, d, f). Two distinct regions are observed in all samples – one is characterized by smooth composition of all elements, while the other one by significant heterogeneity. The former one is associated with the single-phase composition while the latter one by the presence of Cr-rich Laves phase (as proven below in Fig. 6). In the single-phase material, annealing causes homogenization of the chemical composition.

In the Grad 1 sample after homogenization heat treatment, the Cr and Nb EDS lines exhibit significant scattering in the bottom part of the sample, i.e. the Cr rich part. Moreover, at the distance of about 1.2 mm from the bottom part the concentration of Cr rapidly decreases, while concentrations of Ti, Zr and Nb increase. This phenomenon can be attributed to the precipitation of the secondary Laves phase and associated diffusion of Cr to the two-phase part of the sample, cf. the SEM image in Fig. 6a displaying the interface between the single and multi-phase area containing dark secondary phase particles. The similar scattering on the EDS lines of Cr and Nb, were observed in the upper part of the homogenized Grad 2 sample, i.e. again in Cr rich part. In contrast, in the Grad 4 sample significant scattering on the Cr and Zr EDS lines can be observed, indicating the change of the type of the secondary phase or changing their composition. Consistently, the secondary phase particles were observed in the upper part of both Grad 2 and Grad 4 samples (see Fig. 6b and c). The sharp interface between single-phase and multi-phase area is obvious in all samples.

The composition evolution along the building direction (z) of gradient samples after homogenization heat treatment was determined also by local EDS mapping on the area of about $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$, performed

Fig. 7. (a)(c)(e) Microhardness and (b)(d)(f) chemical composition evolution in the Grad 1/Grad 2/Grad 4 samples after homogenization treatment at 1200 °C, respectively. The chemical composition was evaluated from EDS maps measured below the individual indents.

in the vicinity of the microhardness indents. The evolution of both microhardness and composition plotted across the height of the samples is shown in Fig. 7. The initial microhardness of 600 HV in the bottom part of the Grad 1 sample rapidly decreases to the value of 330 HV within the height of 1 mm and then remains constant up to the top surface of the sample, cf. Fig. 7a. The decrease of the microhardness correlates with the rapid decrease of Cr concentration. Similar microhardness dependence on the chemical composition was observed in the Grad 2 sample, cf. Fig. 7c. The rapid increase of Cr concentration and the decrease of Ti/Nb concentration starting from the height of 3.8 mm is accompanied by the gradual increase of the microhardness. The microhardness increases towards the top surface of the sample from the 300 HV in the bottom part to 600 HV in the top part of the sample. In Grad 4 sample, the microhardness gradually increases with increasing z

from 300 HV to 600 HV. There is no apparent change in the microhardness at the height of 1.5 mm, despite the decrease of Ti/Nb concentration and substantial increase of Cr concentration can be observed. It is caused by the fact, that the microhardness of the single-phase area reached value of about 400 HV, similar to values reached in the multi-phase areas of the Grad 1 and Grad 2 samples.

To follow the microstructure evolution in the specific areas of the samples, the thorough microstructure observation in the vicinity of the microhardness indents was performed. Selected SEM micrographs at positions marked by black arrows in Fig. 7a, c, e are shown in Fig. 8. The micrographs are arranged along to the increasing height z. As it is apparent from the SEM images in the first row of Fig. 8, the microstructure of the Grad 1 sample contains secondary phase particles, whose fraction rapidly decreases with increasing z ($z \leq 1$ mm)

Fig. 8. Backscatter SEM images of the (a–c) Grad 1, (d–f) Grad 2 and (g–i) Grad 4 sample in different heights z of the sample, corresponding to specific areas marked by black arrows in Fig. 7a,c, e.

consistently with the decreasing microhardness values and Cr content. In the areas of the constant microhardness values ($z > 1$ mm), the secondary phase particles completely disappeared, cf. Fig. 8c. Similarly, the fraction of secondary phase particles increases with increasing Cr content in the Grad 2 sample, in this case with increasing z . Apart from the Grad 4 sample the size of the particles decreases with their volume fraction. In both Grad 2 and Grad 4 samples, secondary phase evolution correlates with the observed microhardness increase at the upper part of the sample. Based on direct microstructure observations, the parts consisting of single-phase or multi-phase microstructure were labelled in Fig. 7.

The detailed microstructure observations were complemented by the CALPHAD calculations for the chemical compositions shown in Fig. 8. The calculated phase contents at 1200 °C (quenching temperature) are consistent with the experimentally observed ones. As an example, the phases present between temperatures 700 °C and 1500 °C corresponding to the areas in Fig. 8d, e, f are shown in Fig. 9 each with the respective SEM-BSE image in the inset. Indeed, the single phase, observed in the Grad 2 sample, $z = 3.75$ mm, is also present in the calculated diagram in Fig. 9a. For $z = 4$ mm and $z = 5.5$ mm, not only the presence of secondary phase (Laves C15, as confirmed below by XRD measurements) was calculated, but also its amount corresponds well with SEM-BSE observations. For the Grad 2 sample, $z = 4$ mm, there is about 20 % of secondary phase in area fraction, while for $z = 5.5$ mm, there is nearly 50 % of the secondary phase.

EDS mapping enabled to determine the locally averaged chemical composition of the matrix and secondary particles, separately. As it is apparent from Fig. 10, the chemical composition of the secondary phases and the matrix varied significantly. Substantial increase of the Cr

concentration from 10 at.% in the matrix to about 50 at.% in the secondary phase is apparent for both Grad 2 and Grad 4 samples in the edge of the multi-phase area. The concentration of other elements (Ti, Nb, Zr) in the secondary phases is lower as compared to the matrix. The chemical composition of the secondary phases, at the edge of the multi-phase area was found to be the same for both Grad 2 and Grad 4 samples and is about Cr₅₀–Zr₂₃–Nb₁₄–Ti₁₃. However, the chemical composition of the secondary phase changes with increasing z . Concentration of Cr and Ti in the secondary phases gradually increases and decreases, respectively, in both Grad 2 and Grad 4 samples consistently with the evolution of the concentration of Cr and Ti in the matrix. On the other hand, the concentration evolution of Nb and Zr in the secondary phases of Grad 2 and Grad 4 sample differs significantly and exhibits opposite trend. While the concentration of Nb in the secondary phase of the Grad 2 sample increases with increasing z from 14 at.% to the value of 28 at.%, the moderate decrease to about 10 at.% can be observed for the Grad 4 sample. Similarly, the concentration of Zr decreases and slightly increases to the values of 11 at.% and 27 at.% for Grad 2 and Grad 4 samples, respectively. The concentration evolution of Ti, Zr and Nb generally follows the concentration evolution in the matrix. The maximum concentration of Zr and Nb in the secondary phases reached about 27 at.%, while the maximum concentration of Cr was about 57 at.%. The maximum concentration of Ti in the secondary phases is the lowest among other elements and is about 13 at.%.

The phase composition of the single-phase area and areas (bottom, middle and top) along the band containing the secondary phase particles was investigated by XRD. The individual XRD patterns are shown in Fig. 11. The single-phase area was identified as BCC phase, the secondary phase particles observed in SEM were identified as the secondary

Fig. 9. Phase diagrams obtained from CALPHAD calculations for the Grad 2 sample corresponding to the areas of Fig. 8 with different height (a) $z = 3.75$ mm, (b) $z = 4$ mm and (c) $z = 5.5$ mm.

Laves phase type with the cubic C15 structure based on Cr_2Zr . In addition to the Cr and Zr, the Laves phase particles also contain dissolved Ti and Nb atoms as shown above. The lattice parameter of the present Laves phase particles therefore differs from the tabulated one for the model Cr_2Zr phase. As a result, the shift of peaks corresponding to the Laves phase and also to BCC matrix is apparent from Fig. 11. In the Grad 2 sample, the position of peaks is gradually shifted towards the higher angles, due to the increasing concentration of Nb (atomic radius of 146 p.m.) and simultaneous decreasing concentration of Zr (atomic radius of 160 p.m.), which reduces the lattice parameters, and the reflexions are thus observed at higher diffraction angles. Similarly, the observed peak shift towards the lower diffraction angles in the Grad 4 sample is consistent with the increasing and decreasing concentration of Zr and Nb, respectively. Cr_2Zr type Laves phase (Cr51.5-Zr20.6-Nb15.8-Ti12.1), containing additionally dissolved Ti and Nb atoms was observed also in equimolar CrNbTiZr alloy prepared by vacuum arc melting and hot isostatic pressing after the homogenization annealing at 1200 °C for 24 h [38].

To understand better the microhardness evolution in the single-phase area, the values of the atomic size misfit (delta-parameter) were calculated according to formula (2) listed in Ref. [39] based on compositions determined by EDS (Fig. 7b, d, f) and their dependence related to the height z is plotted in Fig. 12. Variation of the atomic size misfit within the gradient samples reflects the extent of the solid solution strengthening. The levels of lattice distortion were found to be

proportional to the atomic size misfit in the TiNbHfTaZr HEA system [40]. Note that the calculation is meaningful only for a single-phase material. In both Grad 1 and Grad 2 samples the atomic size misfit gradually decreases and increases with increasing z , respectively. In the Grad 4 sample, the higher values of atomic size misfit within the height of 2 mm (transition between a single and multi-phase material) results in the highest microhardness in the single-phase material. On the other hand, in the Grad 2 sample, and especially in the Grad 1 sample, the microhardness is independent of the delta-parameter. The practical usage of the atomic size misfit parameter is therefore questioned similarly to previous report [22].

The relation between the chemical and phase composition in compositionally graded CrNbTiZr samples is graphically shown in the form of quaternary phase diagrams in Fig. 13. The investigated compositions corresponding to the single-phase and to two-phase regions are shown in blue and in orange, respectively. The quaternary phase diagram shown in Fig. 13a clearly shows, that the Cr-concentration determines the single-phase and two-phase region. On the other hand, the actual ratio of the three elements in each of the investigated areas is clearly visible in the quaternary phase diagram shown in Fig. 13b.

4. Conclusions

The gradient Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr based complex concentrated alloys with high entropy were prepared from binary equimolar mixtures of

Fig. 10. Chemical composition evolution (in at.%) of the matrix and the secondary Laves phase along the building direction (a)(b) Grad 2 sample and (c)(d) Grad 4 sample. Chemical composition was evaluated from EDS phase maps.

Fig. 11. XRD patterns of the (a) Grad 2 and (b) Grad 4 homogenized samples at different places along the building direction. Patterns were shifted vertically for clarity.

powders, using the additive method L-DED (laser directed energy deposition). High-throughput microstructure characterization of the experimental samples can be summarized as follows.

1. The as-deposited samples with non-linear chemical gradient were subjected to homogenization annealing at 1200 °C/180 h followed by quenching. Homogenization treatment established locally homogeneous microstructure related to the thermodynamic equilibrium at 1200 °C, while the overall chemical gradient was preserved.

2. Cr₂(Zr, Nb, Ti) Laves phase formed during the homogenization heat treatment at the certain chemical compositions. The content of the Laves phase in the Grad 2/4 sample increases along the deposition direction due to the increased Cr content.
3. The chemical composition of Cr₂(Zr, Nb, Ti) Laves phase is determined by the concentration of individual elements in the matrix.
4. The presence of the secondary phase particles significantly increases the microhardness of the material.

Fig. 12. Atomic size misfit as a function of the increasing height for (a) Grad 1 and (b) Grad 2/Grad 4 samples (note that the atomic size misfit is meaningful only for a single-phase region).

Fig. 13. Experimentally determined partial quaternary phase diagrams. Oblique projection from the upper vertex (the position of the crosses corresponds to the actual ratio of the three elements). Blue color single-phase region, orange color two-phase region, symbols represent individual to samples.

- The relation between the chemical and phase composition content was experimentally established and confirmed by ThermoCalc calculations.
- Laser directed energy deposition is a powerful method for the preparation of gradient Cr–Nb–Ti–Zr based complex concentrated alloys and for a high-throughput experimental characterization and construction of multi-dimensional phase diagrams.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17303597> under the CC-BY 4.0 license.

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